

Outbreak Simulation - Third Year Project

Alfred Mountfield

Abstract

Agent-based modelling is a technique that has been quickly growing in popularity in recent years, and which has since come into the foreground of epidemiological research with the COVID-19 pandemic. The health crisis has come with a reliance on modelling for decision-making of government policy, and an influx of new research attempting to utilise it in conjunction with newly appearing data-streams. This presents new challenges, both technical and epidemiological. Designing such models at scale requires the acquisition, and wrangling, of highly-granular input data sets, consideration of low-level computational processes, control of memory layout, and careful architecture.

The work outlined in this report spans the majority of the modelling process. It covers automated generation of realistic synthetic environments, and presents an efficient simulation supporting complex behaviour at large scales. It does so using novel techniques and an array of open-source data-sources to achieve higher fidelity, while also having competitive efficiency. This report also identifies, in the current body of epidemiological research, a systemic lack of differentiation between the two stages of environment generation and simulation. It proposes a solution by decoupling the two components, and evaluates the benefits of doing so within the context of current research. The work builds upon existing efforts, and improves accessibility of agent-based modelling to encourage research that is easier to validate and reimplement.

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1 | Introduction

1.1 Motivation

2020 saw the onset of one of the most prevalent global health crises in the past century. The COVID-19 pandemic led to record-breaking scientific interest, with some estimations stating around 4% of the world's research output was devoted to the coronavirus in 2020 [9]. Within epidemiological research, which covers the study of communicable diseases, a prominent subset focuses on modelling the spread and impact of transmission.

As governments' appreciation for the risk of global infection grew, attention increased on such models in the hopes of evaluating the potential impact of the impending pandemic. Prior to COVID-19 the UK was regarded as the second most prepared country in the world for the emergence of an epidemic [1]. On the 16th of March, the COVID-19 Response Team of Imperial College, headed by Neil Ferguson, a government advisor on the Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE) committee, released a report [11] which attracted significant media attention and criticism. The report claimed to have "informed policymaking in the UK and other countries in recent weeks" [11], and a week afterwards the UK entered its first lockdown.

Underlying the report was an agent-based model (ABM) that was a continuation of research started a couple of decades ago. In that time ABMs have found major prominence within epidemiology and other domains, and have played a pivotal role in government decision making around the world during the pandemic.

Not only does agent-based modelling present an interesting union of technological and domain specific challenges, but the body of research using it is plagued by a series of recurrent problems that are open to be addressed. Included in these problems is a tendency to couple components of a model, which generally inhibits being able to explicitly define the relevant parts. This, accentuated by a proclivity to not release source-code, ultimately results in research that's hard to reimplement and verify. Such problems reached public attention with the critiques levied at the report released by Imperial College.

It's within that context that the work outlined in this report was undertaken. It identifies systemic problems within epidemiological ABM research, and goes on to propose potential solutions to a set of them. It focuses on technical challenges, architectures, and patterns, to enable research that's easier to extend, verify, and importantly, justify.

1.2 Objectives

Almost all ABM research fails to differentiate between two distinct components of the *model*. On one side of the model is the input dataset, defining the starting state of the environment, agents, parameters of infection, contact networks, etc. henceforth referred to as a *synthetic environment*. On the other side is the simulation of the model itself, which will be called a *simulation runner*. The lack of differentiation between the two components results in a series of problems that are explored in more-depth later; in short, it limits confidence in results, reproducibility, and flexibility of the research. It's for these reasons that the work outlined in this report aimed to address two sets of objectives. The first targeted the problem of generating synthetic environments, and the second focused on the implementation of a simulation runner.

1.2.1 Synthetic Environment Generator

- Allow for automated generation of synthetic environments across any given geographical region
- Utilise and explore novel approaches with open-source datasets
- Comprehensively describe the resultant characteristics of the environment
- Output in a well-defined file format, with a focus on language-agnostic accessibility

1.2.2 Simulation Runner

- Utilise the output of the synthetic environment generator
- Efficient implementation in a low-level language
- Support of complex behaviours and agent interactions
- Provide novel approaches or use-cases compared to existing models

Figure 1.1 shows a high-level representation of the resultant components and how they interact to form a modelling pipeline.

Figure 1.1: Architecture of Components

2 | Background

2.1 Epidemiological Modelling

Epidemiological models can be classified into various categories depending on their treatment of variability, chance and uncertainty (deterministic or stochastic), time (continuous or discrete intervals), space (non-spatial or spatial) and the structure of the population (homogenous or heterogeneous mixing) [17].

Modelling is an attempt to simulate simplified processes in a synthetic environment. This commonly takes the form of projective mathematical models based on ordinary differential equations (ODEs), thus being deterministic. It can also materialise in stochastic frameworks that are often used to generate a base of estimates from which to garner trends. Perez and Dragicevic describe models as “basically simplifications of a real-life system, which can contain only some of the essential elements of it - as determined by the researcher” [35]. As they identify, it’s necessary to build your model off assumptions and simplifications of real life processes. Deciding upon appropriate assumptions is a complex task that requires justification.

A common simplification in epidemiology is the use of “Compartmental” models, where the population are assigned into compartments based on their state of infection. Common such labellings of compartments are SIR (Susceptible, Infectious, Recovered) or SEIR (Susceptible, Exposed, Infectious, Recovered). The necessity of such simplifications is evidence of the challenges present in modelling human processes. A particular challenge of interest can be seen by looking at the most common routes of transmission of a communicable disease. These are generally accepted as being through direct contact, fomite, vector-borne, aerosol, or oral exposure [26]. Outside of vector-borne transmission, it is pretty apparent that the other routes are heavily dependent on human interaction and proximity. As such, epidemiological modelling has to consider the contact dynamics of the individuals. To do so involves accounting for the complex network of interactions between people, and the particularities of each interaction.

Examining the challenge of contact networks between people, one would expect spatial structure to play an important role, whether it be living in population dense areas, taking public transit, shopping habits, etc. Despite this, traditional ODE-based models don’t model this directly. Research has been undertaken into the effects of population mixing within a spatially-explicit geography [15], and has found that the spatial structure has significant impact on the underlying dynamics of transmission. As such, with the growth of computational capabilities, epidemiological modelling has moved towards computational models that are able to express spatial heterogeneity.

These computational models often tend to fall into two classes, ABMs, and spatial metapopulation models. Metapopulation models partition the underlying geography into regions, which act as aggregates of the respective population. Similarly to ABMs, the metapopulation approach models underlying contact networks, but instead individual contacts are generalised to that of contacts between regions. In this way the models are able to somewhat represent underlying spatial structures while needing much lower computational resources due to the coarser granularity. And, perhaps most importantly, don’t require intensely detailed input datasets like their agent-based counterparts, instead being able to work more easily with census datasets and other aggregate data sources.

2.2 Agent-Based Models

Agent-based models turn traditional modelling on its head. As a form of “bottom-up” modelling, in contrast to traditional “top-down”, the model is designed from a set of simple low-level properties. These properties interact at scale and result in emergent effects, the intention of which, is to be able to simulate otherwise hard to model interactions found within the complex systems of real life. This allows for the forecasting and exploration of the impact of interventions that otherwise might not be able to be modelled. It’s likely that for these reasons, and the growth of computational power, the use of ABMs has been growing rapidly in recent years [28]. As Macal [28] outlines, the distinguishing factor of ABMs is that the fundamental element of the model is the individual agent, rather than some process or activity as with top-down modelling.

Behaviour-based approaches such as ABMs are particularly suitable to epidemiology, as infection dynamics are heavily reliant upon human behaviour. Of significant interest is the effect of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), recent real-life examples include lockdowns, social distancing, work-from-home orders, and more. These changes to human behaviour were otherwise infeasible to model in top-down approaches due to the lack of data to model off, whereas, depending on implementation, they can be relatively simple to implement in an ABM. The other key benefit as highlighted for this work, is the ability to capture spatial structure. Modelling individuals allows for the expression of positioning and relations within a space. In epidemiology this allows, for example, the differentiation between dynamics in cities and rural populations, or comparison of areas with differing socio-economic status or access to public transit.

2.3 Related Work

In the months since the Imperial report, many ABMs have come out with varying focuses, architectures, and complexities. In contrast to the older Imperial model, modern ABMs attempt to employ newer datasets that weren’t previously available. Google opened public access to “aggregated, anonymized insights they use in products such as Google Maps”. The German government took “regular” advice based on the results of a model utilising mobile phone mobility data [32]. Beyond including more specialised input data, modern models attempt to integrate more complex processes. Examples of ABMs of particular relevance at this time include [2, 11, 22, 25, 32, 33, 36, 37]. As this project was focused on the challenges faced by modelling, rather than specific epidemiological results applicable to COVID-19, there were two papers of particular interest. These are highlighted either for how they motivate a lot of the work undertaken for this report, or for their similarities of approach and capabilities.

2.3.1 CovidSim - MRC Centre for Global Infectious Disease Analysis

The model (called “CovidSim”) that underpinned the Imperial College report was subject to extensive critique due to the initial absence of source-code from the publications. Subsequent criticism then followed the release of the code with collaboration from Microsoft and GitHub [12]. A collaboration that was apparently necessary due to the code being “thousands of lines of undocumented C” written “13+ years ago”, apparently referencing Ferguson’s research that was developed over a series of papers focusing on influenza pandemics [13, 14].

This model is somewhat indicative of other ABMs at the time running at this sort of scale; large, complex projects designed to be massively parallel to utilise large scientific computational power. The current state of the CovidSim repository states that it’s apparently targeting 24 to 32 core Xeon systems, industry-grade processors, and previous papers stated memory usage in the hundreds of gigabytes.

Large-scale, low-level, complex projects with little documentation and intense hardware requirements come with a multitude of obvious challenges. And, as was evidenced by the necessary co-operation with software engineers in industry, it can lead to monoliths that are hard to maintain, understand, and expand. This drew a lot of criticism at the time, and although it was relatively quickly verified both in terms of code integrity, and scientific validation [7], it proves a useful example that outlines barriers to due scientific process. Namely in reproducibility and ease of peer

evaluation. Models that are heavily reliant on implementation and aren't released open-source, and ones that require hard-to-access computational resources to run, open themselves up to avoidable critique that might (and as proven in the case of the work in the Imperial report, did) undermine public-health actions that needed to be taken as a result of the findings.

2.3.2 Large-scale agent-based social simulation - M. Zhang

In their doctoral thesis Zhang outlines a “novel large-scale agent-based social simulation conceptual model” [42]. It establishes a way of thinking about complex models that run at large-scales, illustrated in the work by a sample implementation focusing on Beijing. The model integrates public-transit infrastructure, pattern-generation for more complex agent-based behaviour schedules, and a number of other advanced characteristics rarely found together in models. The sample implementation utilises a previous effort to create a synthetic model of Beijing, therefore being able to focus solely on the epidemiological model, although this brings the aforementioned caveats that come with tying the implementation to the bespoke input dataset.

The conceptual model shares many similarities to the project outlined in this report, although the thesis was discovered late into the process and therefore didn't play an instrumental role in the decision making. It does however, provide an interesting opportunity for comparison and discussion. An example of which, is that, as has been established to be somewhat the trend, the source-code doesn't seem available. This is a major issue as the architecture outlined is, as described, conceptual, and in some parts too tightly tied to conventions of Java, while in other parts it's too weakly described to be reimplemented. The accompanying sample implementation focuses on results and claims, but the missing source-code makes it difficult to use it in representative comparisons, and as such, despite its impressive scope, the project highlights a number of key criticisms of ABM research.

3| Synthetic Environment Generation

3.1 Design and Considerations

3.1.1 The Problem Space

Duplication of work is a common problem in academia which slows down or otherwise inhibits new research; although care should be taken to distinguish between wasted resources in duplicating work, and the essential process of reproducing or verifying research. When almost every similarly-tasks ABM requires a bespoke input dataset, without commonly accepted standards of designing or describing them, it becomes clear that there is progress to be made. This also presents a barrier to entry, as almost all new ABM research is accompanied by development time into either creating appropriate input data, or creating a model to run it. Frequently the focus of the research is on one of these things, and so having to invest substantial effort into the other is undesirable.

Beyond the aforementioned issue of duplication of work, having a bespoke dataset for an ABM can limit its potential to be applied to further research. Models and research are often focused on specific geographies, often ranging from regions equivalent in size to counties, down to the town level. This is partly out of necessity of limiting the scope of research, partly due to efficiency of the simulation, and very often down to the availability of data. Researchers often have the choice of working with consistent but highly aggregated data-sources like census-level datasets, or working with possibly highly-granular and irregular datasets that might only exist for specific small regions. In the latter case, extrapolating to larger regions might be difficult, or plainly incorrect, whereas in the prior case, applying averaged statistics can result in losing the very structures that ABMs hope to be able to model in contrast to more traditional methods.

This ties in to one of the key challenges faced by large-scale ABMs, they require highly-granular input data. Looking at epidemiological ABMs specifically, agreeing with the assumption that the underlying spatial structure of the population plays an essential role in transmission dynamics, directly implies that to adequately model it, representing such spatial characteristics is needed. In the cases of ABMs where the agents are people, the starting set of agents is often called a synthetic population; a dataset designed to appropriately mimic the characteristics of the population it's modelling. For instance, if one wanted to model the spread of a communicable disease in London, then the synthetic population in the model should match identified key attributes of the real-life population of London. This synthetic population is coupled with information on the encompassing synthetic environment, information on buildings, geography, workplaces, schools, etc. Identifying which attributes are substantive is a similar task to that of picking an appropriate model; it's down to the implementer to decide and justify what can be assumed, and what needs to be integrated to be directly modelled.

3.1.2 Identified Key Attributes for Data Sourcing

For the work undertaken in this report, the following attributes, with their reasoning, were isolated as being key focuses for generating synthetic populations.

Spatial Distribution of People

A key idea in this report, is that the spatial structures present in society are quintessential in understanding transmission dynamics. At its core then, one can see that the input dataset requires

realistic distribution of people across the geography. An appropriate dataset should enable the placement of agents within the geography of the synthetic environment in ways that would match real-life densities.

Public Transit Network

Something of specific interest within said spatial structures is the role of public transit systems. This is an aspect that is very rarely covered in ABMs outside of specifically designed simulations where the key focus is transit simulation [27]. In part, this is due to the fact that public transit processes are hard to model, in some ways it would be akin to reimplementing the core of a product like Google Maps, it requires a spatially-explicit multi-modal transit network, scheduling information, statistics on capacities and more.

Beyond its clear use for routing within the simulation, public transit plays an important role in the layout of populations. There is a lot of research into the effects of public transit structure. As Huang [24] outlines, lower-income inner-city residents are subject to “modal mismatch”, ending up disadvantaged by the lack of access to cars in cities whose layouts focus on car transport. Research into commuting habits also shows that commuters’ willingness to travel drops off steeply after a given travelling time [19]. As such it’s clear that public transit infrastructure can have an important effect on commuting habits. Indeed one can look at isochrone maps like those produced by TravelTime¹, diagrams of areas reachable from a given point within a certain time, to see that reachability is not merely determined by distance.

Figure 3.1: An isochrone map generated by TravelTime showing areas reachable by public transport from London in 45 minutes

Examining the isochrones of various areas shows a multitude of irregular shapes, often asymmetric with *islands* of isolated, yet reachable, regions on commuting routes. Despite this, the allocation methods in most papers purely utilise a radial distance to determine a search area. One of the motivating theories of the research in this report is that the spatial structures described by isochrone maps would have direct impacts on the efficacy of NPIs like the local lockdowns put in place by the UK from July 2020. Where, for example, the islands along commuter routes might introduce complex spatial mixing dynamics, inhibiting the attempts to localise interventions.

¹<https://traveltime.com/>

Households

Households are generally accepted to be the places of highest transmission risk when an inhabitant is infected, especially for viruses transmitted similarly to COVID-19 [29]. A person is far more likely to come in physical contact with a household co-inhabitant, as well as more likely to share facilities, etc. Thus increasing the chances of basically every main transmission pathway. An appropriate synthetic population therefore needs realistic groupings of agents into households, the specifics of which can vary; obvious characteristics include distributions of number of people in a household and of ages of inhabitants.

Occupational Locations

For a lot of models, schools and workplaces are grouped into a similar classification. Most agents within the simulation will be part of a contact network at either their work or their school. Designing these networks is an imperfect science, as finding data with which to appropriately measure correctness and validate the designed network is difficult. In general, a few simple attributes are focused on, such as the capacity of these locations, i.e. number of employees and/or number of students. This is also often expanded by partitioning into smaller networks, especially in the case of schools where they might be grouped on a grade/year basis or even per class.

Some models place workplaces randomly according to population density, [13] often without thorough justification. It was postulated as part of this work that this method fails to adequately capture spatial structures seen in real geographies. Specifically, one might not expect to find an equal distribution of workplaces to population density, for the sake of models around planning, cities are often partitioned into various “land use” zones such as “residential”, “entertainment”, or “work” [10, 35]. This helps accentuate that one does not necessarily find a homogeneous mix of residences and workplaces, and workplace-dense areas like the financial district of London might lead to distinct transmission dynamics that would be otherwise missed with the simplification.

3.2 Implementation

3.2.1 Language and Tooling

The pipeline is implemented in Python in a Jupyter notebook to enable fast iteration and interaction at various stages to ensure data is being parsed as intended. Python was selected for rapid development speed, and its ever-growing ecosystem. Of specific interest is the wide range of GIS (Geographic Information System) utilities that simplify the otherwise complex issue of working with spatial data, as well as packages that make API access easier.

As the pipeline is a form of pre-computation, in that it generates a file once to be used as an input across a set of simulation runs, efficiency isn’t of main concern. This means that the subtleties required to implement fast Python code can largely be ignored for most components. IPython provides a suite of useful “cell magic”s for rapid benchmarking, and Jupyter’s integrated support of packages like Matplotlib² vastly improves the experience of working with spatial data.

3.2.2 Output Format

For the structure of output, a few avenues were initially identified, namely JSON, XML, and Protocol Buffers (Protobuf). All three have rich ecosystems around them, which would remove unnecessary work with integration, and JSON and XML have the benefits of being readable in a raw file. That however, was not viewed as important for a dataset that can run into the millions of entities, and for that reason a space efficient format was prioritised for writing, storage, transfer, and reading benefits. Beyond this, schemas in JSON and XML are verbose and somewhat finicky to work with, whereas Protobuf has concise and easily readable schemas. Upon deciding on something similar to Protobuf, further investigation lead to the FlatBuffers format.

The choice of FlatBuffers leads to a number of advantages as an output for a synthetic environment. The schema is similarly concise to Protobuf, giving a clear and easily readable (and

²<https://matplotlib.org/>

updatable) definition of the data. As a binary format, it doesn't provide readability of the data itself, but does benefit from reduced size from much more efficient encoding schemes. Both FlatBuffers and Protobuf provide code-generation methods across a variety of languages, this removes an often time-intensive step of writing a custom parser for the schema, something that needs to be maintained in sync with the data. Instead, the generated code is responsible for providing an API in your app to the data, and handles all reading and writing functionality. A large benefit of FlatBuffers over Protobuf is the lack of a deserialisation step, it was designed for performance-critical applications such as games, where reading directly from the binary data can be a large advantage. The result is lower memory consumption³, and much simpler generated code.

While FlatBuffers may not prove to be the ideal output format for synthetic environments going forward, it still provides a possible avenue to solve some of the issues identified earlier. It's clear that there needs to be an effort to standardise, or at least create a framework for, the input state used in ABMs in research; general descriptions of the various collected data sources, or generic pseudo-code for the processes can too often fail to describe the underlying spatial structure which directly inhibits efforts to verify and reproduce the method.

3.2.3 Selected Data Sources

Spatial Distribution of People

The central entity of an agent-based model is of course the agent itself, in this case representing a person within the simulation. Taking the Imperial Model as an example, shows that "placing" agents within the simulation is usually determined by a dataset for population count or density. A number of sources are available for this sort of data, Landscan⁴ being one that was frequently used in the past, for example in the Imperial Model, which provides estimates of counts of people in "pixels" of ~1km x ~1km on a rasterised image. For this project, the datasets produced by WorldPop⁵ were selected, as they provide population counts to a much finer resolution of 100m created by a selection of methods, including being adjusted to match estimates from the United Nations. WorldPop has a focus on underdeveloped nations, and has a lot of research into making realistic estimates in situations where data might be missing, and therefore integrating it into the pipeline would improve the pipeline's ability to model areas with worse information.

Public Transit Network

Practical datasets of public transit networks are neither common, nor readily accessible. It's only in recent years that there has been a well-spread effort to standardise transit data, largely spear-headed by Google in 2006 with the release of the *Google Transit Feed Specification* [21]. As the format was accepted in more places, it was renamed to the *General Transit Feed Specification* (GTFS) in 2009. Importantly for this project, the specification describes both the layout of a multi-modal public transit network, and its respective timetabling.

Since 2009 many transit operators have begun to release their timetabling information in GTFS, and the US currently has a unified "National Transit Map" that was first released in 2016 [38]. Despite this, most other public transit providers in the world have a much less unified approach, and a readily-accessible and sufficient collation of GTFS providers doesn't currently exist. Attempts have been made, the GTFS Data Exchange which ran from 2016-2018 attempted to provide a place for agencies to upload GTFS feeds. TransitFeeds / OpenMobilityData⁶ is currently active but even popular feeds in a densely populated area like the Docklands Light Railway in London are missing. The best unified source currently seems to be that of TransitLand⁷, a somewhat "open-source" service similarly dedicated to unifying GTFS feeds into a single point which, from initial investigation, seems to contain a fairly comprehensive covering.

As the [hopeful] intention of the Synthetic Environment generator is to be fully automated, the standardised GTFS format seems to be the only solution to allow the process to stay general.

³https://google.github.io/flatbuffers/flatbuffers_benchmarks.html

⁴<https://landscan.ornl.gov/>

⁵<https://www.worldpop.org/>

⁶<https://transitfeeds.com/>

⁷<https://www.transit.land/>

Figure 3.2: WorldPop 100m² U.N. Adjusted clipped to Greater London

TransitLand seemed to provide a unified API which would allow the automated retrieval of data within a geographic boundary, similar to the rest of the workflow within the generator, however it proved to be non-viable for the time-period of this work. At time of writing, the TransitLand API is migrating from v1.0 to v2.0, including a migration of the database of GTFS feeds. The publicly accessible v1.0 API has a similar data-quality issue as other GTFS aggregators, whereas the v2.0 API seems to have fixed that, but is currently only accessible through the web interface, or through an API that’s unsuitable to the process. An inquiry to the TransitLand team about timing of the release of their full API lead a refusal to give an estimate and as such, other avenues had to be explored. It should be noted that a conclusion of the research in this report is that GTFS is the viable format for support and TransitLand seems like the most likely place to be used in automated approaches in the future. These qualities are key for making research accessible and transferable, allowing consistency in comparison between different regions.

With the inability to use TransitLand’s API during development, it was decided to focus the generation on areas within the UK. Despite having many open datasets from the Office of National Statistics, the UK does not provide a comprehensive aggregate GTFS dataset. Instead of investing a lot of time attempting to manually download and collate the relevant transit operator’s feeds, it was decided to use the non-GTFS dataset created by Gallotti and Barthelemy in 2015 [16], which provides a well-formatted aggregate dataset for the UK, complete with a form of scheduling information which would serve for proof of concept. This dataset was picked for ease of parsing of the format, and its comprehensive cover of the different modes of transport in the UK, although another option would have been to use the Traveline National Dataset [40].

Households

As most ABMs work off static networks, or similarly generalised implementations, household generation/allocation is a mostly simple procedure. Placements are assumed to be directly mapped to population density, and as such the process generally follows something akin to:

Figure 3.3: The UK Multi-Layer Transit Graph clipped to Greater London

```

while len(tile.people) != 0:
    size = get_household_size_from_distribution()
    inhabitants = tile.people.pop(size)
    new_household(inhabitants, pos=random_pos_in_tile(tile))

```

Randomly placing the house within the tile is likely sufficient even for a model as spatially explicit as the one covered by this report. Taking the opportunity for exploration however, the pipeline utilises OpenStreetMap (OSM) data to inform the choices about locations for the placements of households. In certain locations, especially built-up areas like London and other densely-populated regions, OSM has relatively detailed data on building geometries. These geometries are tied to attributes including indications of purpose, for example tourist attractions, places of work, or, of interest here, types of residence. Therefore, as a proof of concept, the pipeline utilises building geometries from OSM that are tagged as being one of “residential”, “apartments”, “flats”, “house”, or “yes”; the latter tag representing building geometries that generally have no attribution. The results of such a query is demonstrated in Figure 3.4.

This leads to a certain number of false positives but as will be discussed, the approach as a whole underestimates the number of residencies anyway so in some ways this is beneficial. From visual inspection in conjunction with the population count raster, it appears to fairly represent where one would expect to find residential buildings for densely populated areas. For more rural areas however, or even just suburban areas further from the centre, the data quickly becomes sparse.

The benefits of having fine-grained data is something worth further research. While the somewhat random placement of households might be adequate in simpler models, when efforts are made to include public transport infrastructure and other complexities into a simulation, this might not prove to be the case. The small-scale distances agents might have from nearby bus stops and similar could possibly have an affect on routing and mixing dynamics. It’s also worth noting that the pipeline does not have to be limited to epidemiological modelling, and having realistic building placements alongside road-networks is likely to be essential for scenarios such as realistic traffic modelling.

Should the improved granularity of the data prove to be something of worth, further data sources could be combined with the OSM data approach. Recent ventures have been made into identifying building footprints from satellite imagery, most often through machine-learning methods. Unfortunately the already-generated datasets found during research in this project were limited to geographies like the US and Australia, [31] and generating new ones for regions of in-

Figure 3.4: OpenStreetMap building geometries within Tower Hamlets, London

terest was well out of scope of the work undertaken here. Nevertheless, these building footprint datasets could be combined with land-use classifications, to estimate the number of residences in a way representative of real-life.

Occupational Locations

This project was able to explore occupational locations for generic “workplaces” allocated to all agents between the age of 17 and 67. The preceding work of recreating the Imperial model also covered schools which requires a similar approach for allocation, although that wasn’t implemented here. The distribution for workplace sizes that was included in the Imperial work was utilised [14].

Similarly to residences, OSM data was utilised to inform the placement of workplaces rather than random placements according to population density. While this needs further research for rigorous justification, it is likely that merely randomly placing workplaces is less representative than that of randomly placing households. As outlined in Figure 3.1.2, there’s evidence that there is a heterogeneous layout of workplaces, even when considering the effects of population density. Utilising OSM data provides an exploration into a possible technique to fairly model the otherwise hard to describe heterogeneous distributions present in reality, by utilising crowd-sourced real-life positions of places of work.

Utilising a combination of tags on OSM queries, an aggregate set of possible workplaces was built, namely POIs with the “shop”, or “amenity” tags, general data with the “office” tag, and buildings with the “office” or “offices” tags. This specific selection of tags aimed at capturing a variety of possible workplaces, while accounting for some of the inconsistencies that can be found in the crowd-sourced OSM data.

It’s important to note that these queries are an experiment to see the viability of this approach. The data from the queries is meant to bias the stochasticity of synthetic environment generation towards being more representative of the structures seen real life. It is not meant to exactly recreate real-life structures as that would require much more granular data on the aspects of each workplace, and the integrity of OSM data would become a more prominent issue. Figure 3.5 highlights the density of workplace data-points within Canary Wharf, with lower densities found in the more residential areas. Comparison with Figure 3.4 matches logical expectations of density of the two sets.

Figure 3.5: Results of the workplace query from OpenStreetMap within Tower Hamlets, London, with Canary Wharf highlighted

The additional attributes (i.e. anything that isn't position data) of the query were ignored for the purposes of this work, but would provide interesting avenues for future research, especially when looking at trying to model places that have featured prominently in NPIs, such as supermarkets which are often missing from models. Having that data available provides more options to future modelling efforts, without requiring a large investment of development time into trying to massage distinct data-streams into compatible formats.

3.2.4 Methodology

Spatial Data and Projections

One can see an example of the challenges faced in working with spatial data by looking at geographic projections. Spatial data is defined via a coordinate reference system (CRS), the most familiar of which is likely to be WGS84 (otherwise known as EPSG:4326), which describes positions in terms of the angular measures known as latitude and longitude. Coordinate reference systems have an associated projection, which necessarily distorts the earth's curved surface when wanting to work on flat euclidean space. This causes issues when trying to work with euclidean distance calculations, as the non-projected WGS84's units of latitude and longitude are inconsistent in distance, as arc-seconds represent different distances nearer and further from the equator for example. To fairly apply something like nearest-neighbour analysis it becomes necessary to project to a coordinate system that uses a unit such as metres. For the purposes of the the implementation, it became necessary to focus on the UK due to accessibility of public transit data, and therefore EPSG:27700 was chosen. The CRS is the British National Grid and is used for the UK Ordnance Survey, which minimises distortions of the UK, and uses the metre as the unit allowing for easy distance calculations.

While reprojecting works fine for data consisting of points, one can see the effect this has on the structure of geometries, and indeed even the values, by looking at attempts to project the population raster to match other data-sources. This is illustrated in Figure 3.6.

Looking at the population counts in the titles of each image within the figure, one can see that the sampling method chosen can vastly change the population estimates of the geography in

Figure 3.6: Comparisons of population count of the Isle of Dogs, London, when projected to EPSG:27700 using Rasterio with various sampling methods

question. For this reason the the raster was converted to dataset of points by taking the centroids of each cell and attributing their population before projecting to EPSG:27700. Household allocation was then implemented with a tolerance to account for distortion from the projection.

Household Allocation and Person Generation

The population raster defines where people are expected to live, and as such the household generation process and initialisation of agents are naturally connected. During the household allocation process which is described shortly, agents are generated according to a very basic probability distribution for ages. This is partnered with a method that somewhat hard-codes logic for matching adults with children within the households to create networks that somewhat represent families. For further research an appropriate model should be implemented to encapsulate census data and more representative characteristics.

The actual geometries supplied by OSM vary in type, some are made of multiple polygonal geometries, while others are as simple as a point marking the general location of a building. As the complex geometries weren't viewed as important for the simulation, beyond being a visual nicety, they were converted to their respective centroids (another calculation that requires a CRS with a unit of euclidean distance), giving a cohesive set of points, each corresponding to a building.

Another aspect that is often overlooked by most models, is the lack of a bijection between households and residential buildings; it is possible that sharing a lift in an apartment building, or using shared facilities like a gym, could lead to transmission between households. While this wasn't explored within the simulation's implementation outlined in this paper, the pipeline was designed to cater to that research, utilising the data provided by OSM, and some novel techniques, to estimate locations and types of residencies. To do this, the output dataset contains three classifications of residency:

- *House*: Intended to represent a standard house where one might find up to two distinct

households, includes properties that might be referred to as “converted flats” in the UK.

- *Small Flat*: A residence that can contain up to 10 households
- *Large Flat*: A residence that can contain up to 150 households

These classifications were chosen as a proof-of-concept for the approach, while hopefully modelling some of the heterogeneous nature of residences. The capacities were chosen as ballpark figures from initial readings, and a well-balanced set of classifications would need further justification and reasoning.

Each building from the OSM data is attributed to one of these three categories before the household allocation process, and specifically, all data tagged with “apartments” or “flats” is attributed to the “Small Flat” classification, and “House” otherwise. The process through which households are allocated, and the preliminary “Person” objects are created, is described by the following Python-esque pseudocode:

```
# create a lookup of residential buildings that are
# close to the centre of each tile
residences_in_radius = query_radius(tile_centres, residential_buildings)

for num_people_at_tile in population_raster:
    for _ in range(num_people_at_tile):
        nearby_residences = residences_in_radius[tile_centre]
        for residence in nearby_residences:
            # Try and find a non-full household at the residence
            possible_households = choose_non_full_household(residence)
            if len(possible_households) != 0:
                chosen_household = random_choice(possible_households)
                break
            # Otherwise create a household if the residence isn't full
            else if residence.has_household_capacity():
                chosen_household = make_household(residence)
                break
        # All residences were full, so one needs to be upgraded
        else:
            # can't size up an already largest residence
            candidates = non_largest(nearby_residences)
            chosen_residence = random_choice(candidates)
            upgrade(chosen_residence)
            chosen_household = make_household(chosen_residence)
            break

    add_new_person(chosen_household)
```

The exact implementation covers more subtleties and complications than would be feasible to concisely represent the process of here. The population counts at each 100m² tile are matched up with the OSM building data through queries of a KDTree (a radius of 300m was selected for the initial implementation). Failures to find a residence to upgrade are also tracked to check for an error rate, this indicates that the OSM data had enough missing buildings that the population estimates couldn't fit within them. This happened extremely rarely within the areas where OSM data was detailed, but the growth of it in locations with worse data demonstrates a clear limitation of using OSM data on its own.

Occupational Locations

The results from the OSM query were aggregated into a set of points in a similar method to that described for residences. Each workplace co-ordinate in the set is matched with a maximum capacity drawn from the distribution described in the supplementary material of the Imperial paper [14]. The algorithm behind allocating workplaces is novel, utilising some common approaches from games for efficiency. Allocation algorithms are often one of the slowest components of the population generation, as it generally involves distance calculations between the sets of workplaces and people, both of which can number into the millions in size. As the supplementary material states, “it is very easy to find algorithms which are $O(N^2)$ and take days to allocate large populations”

[14], which can be a limiting factor when wanting to generate large synthetic environments, or even just during development.

The procedure implemented for this work manages to have efficient run times despite having more complex logic than most generation methods. As described in subsection 3.1.2, it was hypothesised in this work that the locations of a person’s household and workplace are not directly affected by distance, but instead the travel-time between the two. Although direct research upon this matter wasn’t found in the research for this project, comparing the performance of a synthetic population modelled with and without this idea could give indication to its validity. As such, the workplace allocation process utilises a combination of both distance, and time associated through routing via public transport; should this prove to have a meaningful affect on the underlying dynamics, the distance calculation could be replaced by a similar routing function on the road networks. It was shown in the work that these could be easily accessed and operated on through the OSM packages.

One of the largest problems involved in allocation is the selection of an adequate workplace given an agent, or vice versa. A rudimentary solution might be to pick a random one from the set of all workplaces, however this would completely ignore all the problems previously mentioned. The resultant procedure therefore had a number of challenges to deal with, which of note included, finding a set of workplaces within a radius of a point, finding a set of households within radius of a point, and selecting a realistic path between two nodes on the public transit network.

Distance Queries: The first two problems prove difficult only when working at large scales, in some ways it resembles that of a nearest-neighbour (NN) problem, of which many solutions exist. Unfortunately at the scales focused on for this work, the sets of workplaces, and agents both number in the hundreds of thousands to millions. Attempting to change the perspective of the problem by allocating workplaces-to-households, or households-to-workplaces, doesn’t change the end dynamic of a quadratic solution for the naive solution. This is apparent especially when considering public transit, there are two necessary NN queries, compared to the one for the distance-only based method, one for nearby transit nodes to the workplace, and another for nearby households to the destination transit node. Efficient approaches for radius queries on two spatially-explicit sets are often handled by KD-Trees or similar methods. However experiments into these showed that both RAM usage and run-times grew rapidly with input size and it was infeasible to run on even a computer with 24GB of RAM and large paging file. Approximate nearest-neighbour solutions exist, and one of particular interest for future implementation if necessary is one utilising a space-filling curve to reduce it to a single-dimensional problem space [30]. However to avoid blowing up the scope of the project a novel, but simpler, approach was taken.

As exact nearest-neighbour searches aren’t required, one can estimate distances between entities by subdividing the space into a grid of a configurable resolution. This allows neighbouring cells to be directly indexed rather than looping over all entities to find nearby ones (this acts similarly to the spatial enumeration provided by binary space partitioning). This alone doesn’t provide enough of an efficiency gain however, as the distance accessible by a car within an average commute time will generally be in the tens of kilometres (60km was arbitrarily chosen for proof-of-concept assuming one hour with an average speed of 60km/h). These large radii especially cause issues in dense geographies, as one query alone would be large enough to include the majority of London. Each person-workplace allocation requires a random sample from that radius, which translates to a sample across potentially millions of entities.

To solve this, a further layer of abstraction is added, instead of the grid being a direct lookup where each cell has a list of elements, a secondary grid is created whose values at each cell are the length of that respective list. In other words, two grids are maintained, one partitioning the space which provides a direct lookup of elements within each cell, and the other providing a count of the number of elements at each cell. This reduces the problem from potentially sampling across N workplaces, to sampling across M counts, where M is the number of cells in the grid of desired resolution. To do so, an index of the *counts* grid is sampled, where each index is weighted by the value (approximate number of elements at that cell).

There are a few caveats of this approach, the spatial enumeration by itself means the method is approximate as calculated distances depend on chosen resolution, but also the sampling method is necessarily imperfect. If the *counts* grid was dynamic, then each sample would require recalculating

the lengths of the lists of elements, which depending on language implementation could be constant or linear for each list, however as the sampling is used for allocation, each element would need to be removed from future contention. Removing elements from lists in Python is linear with the length of the list, and doing this upon every sample would remove the benefits of the approach. As such, an algorithm was designed to recalculate the weights intermittently.

```
def get_sample(counts, mask):
    # each cell's weight is the proportion of the total
    probabilities = counts[mask] / total(counts[mask])

    chosen_indices = random_choice(cell_indices, probabilities,
                                  num_samples=cache_size)

    return chosen_indices

# a generator to find an unemployed person within a radius around a point
def unemployed_within_dist(centre, dist, failure_threshold=200, cache_size=200):
    counts = count_unemployed_per_cell()
    # create a mask to only select elements within the radius
    mask = create_circular_mask(centre, radius)
    chosen_indices = iter(get_sample(counts, mask))

    failures = 0

    while True:
        try:
            chosen_index = next(iter_chosen_indices)
        except StopIteration: # used up the cache, populate by resampling
            chosen_indices = iter(get_sample(counts, mask))
            continue
        try:
            next_person = unemployed_cells[chosen_index].pop()
        except IndexError: # no unemployed people in that bucket
            failures += 1
            # had a lot of failures, refresh the probabilities
            if failures > failure_threshold:
                failures = 0
                chosen_indices = iter(get_sample(counts, mask))
            continue

        yield next_person
```

Realistic Routes on Public Transit In the absence of direct research on the actual spatial structure of commutes to model off, attempts were made to logically reason about an individual's commute. Out of related research, the most applicable data was found to be that of the length of commutes (in terms of journey time). As such, the process focuses on commuting time as the main input parameter. Given a starting point (in this case the node near either the workplace or the household depending on starting-perspective), the problem of choosing a sensible destination is not straight-forward. There is a lot of research on path-*finding* in graphs, but none was found on *realistic* path-*generation*, probably largely due to the specificity of the domain. A naive attempt of picking a random origin-destination pair would lead to uncontrollable, and unrealistic, distributions of commutes.

One possible approach then, would be to travel on a random edge from the starting node, and continue to do so until the chosen commuting time had been reached. This, unsurprisingly, resulted in convoluted paths one wouldn't expect from a commute, and as such the random selection needed to be biased in some way. Commuting has the intention of getting from A to B, with the obvious desire to do so as quickly/painlessly as possible (for the purposes of this research, a focus was taken on travel-time for simplicity). From this, one could possibly choose a destination bearing, and pick random edges with a bias for that bearing, resulting in a more directed and purposeful path. While being relatively efficient, this approach failed to capture some of the underlying features of the network, some edges might be off-bearing and thus missed, despite possibly being components of a much faster path, and therefore more likely to be taken.

These attempts made it clear that even a generative stochastic approach, like described, would most likely need shortest-path information to effectively pick destinations along a sensible path.

Figure 3.7: Density of 50,000 samples in a radius around Tower Hamlets from a grid with a cell size of 100 metres

Due to this, a simpler approach was chosen that relies on computing all shortest-paths from a point. Given a set of shortest paths, one can then sample from those within the desired commuting range to pick a destination that's reachable within desired time, which is equivalent to the isochrone maps described earlier which represented the structure the process is hoping to model. All shortest-paths is a compute-intensive process, however a number of subtleties made the process viable on the scales tested. Firstly, as the aim is to choose origin-destination pairs, the actual path information can be discarded during calculation, instead keeping only the total weight of each path which drastically decreases both memory and CPU usage. Furthermore, the commuting-times can be chosen to have a cut-off value, which also greatly decreases run-time as the search is able to prune most pairs even on large graphs. Finally, optimised libraries exist and are readily accessible for this task, reducing development time.

Workplace Allocation With those two sets of problems solved, the workplace allocation process settled on something as described by the following pseudo-code. It's worth noting that the actual implementation covers edge-cases and has optimisations including ones that prune possibilities once proven to be exhausted.

```

for workplace in shuffled(workplaces):
    if successes >= num_to_allocate: # allocated all unemployed
        break

    transport_options = [TransportType.PUBLIC_TRANSIT, TransportType.DRIVING,
                        TransportType.CYCLING, TransportType.WALKING]

    nearby_transit_nodes = get_nearby_transit_nodes(workplace)
    # for radii of walking, cycling, and driving
    unemployed_in_radius = unemployed_within_dist(workplace.centre)

    for _ in range(workplace.capacity):
        # shuffle the transport according to probabilities
        shuffled_transport_options = iter(shuffled(transport_options))

        while (person_id == None):
            transport_type = next(shuffled_transport_options)

            if transport_type == TransportType.PUBLIC_TRANSIT:
                source_node = random_choice(nearby_transit_nodes)
                while (person_id == None):
                    dest_node = random_choice(nodes_in_commute_dist[source_node])
                    person_id = next(unemployed_near_node[dest_node])
            else:
                person_id = next(unemployed_in_radius[transport_type])

        if person_id:
            people_to_workplaces[person_id] = workplace.index
            successes += 1
            if successes >= num_to_allocate: # allocated all unemployed
                break
        else:
            break

```

3.3 Evaluation

In order to evaluate the final state of the pipeline, a focus will be taken on its differentiating factors compared to existing approaches, its ease of use, and its potential.

3.3.1 Novel Improvements

The implemented pipeline has a much higher spatial fidelity when compared to most models in literature working on large-scales. Rather than random placements of households and workplaces within the rasterised grid, the pipeline utilises OSM data to be much more representative of real life. The benefits of such high fidelity are open to discussion for epidemiological modelling, however this sets a foundation to be able to quantitatively compare the affects of high and low fidelity. Furthermore as the pipeline does not have to be limited to epidemiology, the work could prove very useful for other common applications of agent-based modelling like transit simulations.

OSM Data Quality

The design proposes a way of handling and utilising the higher fidelity of OpenStreetMap data. Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5 highlight its capability to capture spatial heterogeneity beyond the standard approaches of defining zones or districts. As such, the design reduces the problem down to one of data-quality. Looking at Figure 3.8 one can see that a large portion of the populated areas on raster (seen as the purple grid in the background) have associated residential building geometries as expected (the red geometries). However towards the south west and south east one can see populated areas without associated residential buildings.

Future endeavours should aim to evaluate the impact of this, and if needs be, rectify it. The open-source Rust traffic simulator, *A/BStreet*⁸, a project that was contributed to during this

⁸<https://github.com/a-b-street/abstreet>

Figure 3.8: Aggregate Greater Manchester dataset with missing buildings

work, poses a possible approach to solving this. It generates households and buildings along empty spaces on road networks retrieved from OSM, and this could be improved by only generating households when there’s a mismatch between population density and building density. To be more representative of real-life however, it would be interesting to supplement OSM data with building footprint datasets. Microsoft has released a set of datasets of building footprint data using ML on satellite imagery, however it’s currently limited to the US, Canada, Australia, Uganda, and Tanzania [31]. It is likely that these datasets will grow in availability in coming years and pose an interesting avenue for integration into microsimulations.

Public Transit

The inclusion of public transit data in the allocation processes and the resultant synthetic environment is a strong distinguishing feature when compared to competitors. The inclusion in the output file provides the possibility to study the impact of public transport on transmission, something of particular interest in highly-connected mega-cities. Whereas its integration within the actual generation pipeline presents as a prototypical effort to model the complexities of commuter behaviour and city structure.

There are existing models that have some form of integration of public transport, MATSIM [23], SUMO [27], etc. However these either require manual sourcing and data-wrangling of transport data, something found through this project to be extremely difficult to do, or have import utilities that have serious data quality issues. Beyond this the frameworks have a focus on mobility rather than epidemiology. For instance, typical use-cases of MATSIM are for simulating a single day rather than weeks and months of in-simulation time that are generally used for epidemiological needs. Trying to extend this and incorporate more behaviours can be awkward and unintuitive.

The pipeline solves this for the UK, implementing the necessary data massaging to integrate the public-transit graph with the other data-streams and select the relevant region. The current restriction to the UK is something that is definitely worth further work, as the GTFS file format provides the necessary data in a consistent and well-defined format, which is essential for a implementation that is widely applicable. With the imminent release of the TravelLine API 2.0, there should be an open-source, usable, and general, interface to use which should make the pipeline applicable to any country.

3.3.2 Ease of Use

As the generation process is decoupled from the simulation runner, it was able to be implemented in Python which is commonly accepted to be one of the most approachable languages, and indeed one of the most popular in research. Low-level programming knowledge is therefore not a barrier to entry. This is capitalised on by leveraging its strong ecosystem to do the heavy-lifting, and the

end result is a tool with minimal input but complex functionality. While the notebook is long, it provides many points for intuitive verification, and the only necessary modification is the initial few cells of configuration. Such modification includes things like, supplying a file name, and selecting a geographical bounding box. Beyond those initial parameters, the pipeline is fully automated and is capable, on a consumer desktop, of producing small regions of under a million people within half an hour, and larger regions of under ten million people in a few hours.

This was validated throughout the development process of the simulation runner, a number of synthetic environments were generated to investigate the difference in behaviours of relatively population-dense cities such as Manchester compared to a much less dense county of Devon. It also provided an easy way to create a model of central London, and one that included a large part of the commuter ring to incorporate dynamics of transport, dense and sparse populated areas, and more. This also made it easy to generate test files of varying size and population for various benchmarks.

Visual Interfacing

At key points within the pipeline, visualisations provide the researcher with insights into the current state providing confidence and allowing for mistakes to be picked up earlier. An example of this is seen in Figure 3.9 which provides an aggregate view of the selected data-streams for the region. This rapidly provides insight into the population densities and structure, verifying the quality of the OSM data, and ensuring it has all been parsed as expected. Such visualisations are essential in being able to intuitively understand the underlying spatial data, in contrast to the incomprehensible abstract nature of some input models.

Figure 3.9: A visualisation from the generator showing the aggregate of the data-streams for Wales

Instant Access

It's worth noting that the pipeline has been purposefully limited to using open-source data streams. This removes a common problem of needing to request academic data access, acquiring an API key or license, etc. This can inhibit efforts to validate and reimplement models, and licensed data-sources can result in researchers not having the right to include the input data or even derivatives alongside the research.

Well-Defined Output Format

Contrastingly this pipeline's well-defined output format is perfectly suited to inclusion alongside research. It provides a way of explicitly defining the input of a simulation, and allows for retrospective analysis of populations later on should other properties be deemed worthy of research despite them not being originally highlighted. Drawing justified comparisons between models can be extremely difficult due to this, the tight integration of the input model and the simulation model means that two simulations models of London might not be comparable due to differing input characteristics.

Beyond this, other benefits were identified during development of the simulation runner. Having a schema with generated code facilitated iterative development, and allowed for development of the two parts independently.

3.3.3 Extensibility

Beyond the possible improvements regarding data quality and public transport data access, the pipeline presents numerous avenues for future research. Due to the distinct steps, there are clear places to add further functionality. Some examples of such functionalities that were deemed noteworthy during development are:

- Hooks for using census data during Person initialisation
- School Generation and Allocation
- Inclusion of Hospitals
- Inclusion of Care-homes
- Integration of Shops and other places of interest

Investigation could be made into using the pipeline for transit microsimulations and other areas of urban spatial science. Throughout development the schema provides a place for defining breaking-changes and updates to the synthetic environment format and ensures that all resultant properties of the environment are explicitly defined and known.

4 | Simulation Runner

4.1 Design and Considerations

There is a growing plethora of ABM-based epidemiological research, especially in the wake of COVID-19, and as such, to benefit from the creation of yet another model it should either validate/assess existing research, or present something novel. These goals were kept in mind during the initial stages of exploratory development.

4.1.1 High-Level Objectives

Modular Architecture

The need for modularity is two-fold; for one, the scope of this project allowed for a limited amount of work and as such, pragmatically, the final state of implementation would be missing many desirable functionalities. Being able to extend the implementation, with further behaviours and complexities, without needing to re-architect the entire project is essential for the potential longevity of the work. Secondly, a common reason for starting ABMs from scratch for new research is the specificity of existing designs; tightly-coupled components make it obtrusively difficult to introduce new complex behaviours. This can make it impossible to retro-fit the ability to analyse the impact of new methods of NPIs, instead needing a new model. A recent example being something like contact-tracing [2].

Dynamic Positioning for Agents

Many ABMs, including CovidSim [14], have a static social contact network as a foundation. In such models, instead of agents *physically* moving about their environment, their interactions and relative exposure to each other is defined by a weighted graph, with networks like the household being weighted more heavily than that of the workplace. A very common compromise is to generate “random networks by assuming that each person in the modelled population can come into contact with anyone else in the population” [25]. It greatly simplifies the social contact dynamics of people in a population but it has no method of capturing the underlying spatial structures that are created by shopping characteristics, transit options, choice of leisure activities, et cetera.

Not “physically” moving agents can have large benefits in efficiency that come with keeping memory locations static. CovidSim uses probabilities that are constant across all time-steps with the intention of it averaging out, meaning that an agent is as likely to be infected by their colleague at 4 in the morning as they are during work. This might not necessarily be an issue, as almost any disease that is studied has a longer incubation period than a day, and as such directly consequent interactions are unlikely to factor in. Some models attempt to add stronger temporal-dependence into their implementations, the Global-Scale Agent Model (GSAM) [34] for instance uses a set of probability *distributions* for agents to bias interactions with certain social networks based on time of day. This somewhat more closely models what one would expect in real-life, being more likely to interact with a colleague during work hours, a family member outside of those hours, etc.

A problem with these static approaches however, is that it creates an extra layer of abstraction that makes it harder to reason about choices and quantify them. Agent-based modelling is focused on emergent properties from the combination of many simple behaviours, and the closer those behaviours are to their real-life counterparts, the easier it is to justify parameters and decisions.

Creating and justifying the mathematical decisions behind a set of probability curves for various aspects of the day could be a large barrier for incoming research, especially when such underlying data might not exist for the region in question.

As such, the designed model focused on supporting dynamic positions for agents, as this should allow for greater opportunities to implement more complex behaviours. Having agents move within the simulation will introduce more implementation complexity but should allow for easier addition of things like contact simulations in public transport, supermarkets, shops, hospitals, etc. Effectively it creates dynamic contact networks without needing to think about how to model and modify complex graph topologies, whose dynamics might change differently depending on the simulation state. Modelling changes in behaviour when, for example, NPIs are introduced like designated shopping times for the vulnerable, are much easier to reason about when thinking about mobility, rather than abstract contact network graphs.

Focus on Efficiency

Beyond being an interesting technical challenge, having an efficient implementation has more benefits than might be immediately apparent; after all, long-running simulations aren't uncommon in research, especially on such large scales. Indeed, as ABMs [generally] shouldn't be used as quantitatively predictive tools, immediate feedback and quick run-times may seem superfluous. The time to results on a single simulation run isn't the only concern however. Perhaps the most directly impactful, is that slow run-times can greatly inhibit development speed, which is often a limiting factor of scope; being able to rapidly test the simulation allows for a tighter feedback loop for the developer. Beyond development, faster run-times have a direct impact on the ability to be confident in conclusions drawn from the simulations. Many ABMs rely on stochasticity to search for common emergent properties and avoid anomalies; as such being able to run more simulations, in parallel or sequentially, can have a compound effect on the ability to confidently claim emergent behaviours.

As well as reinforcing conclusions, multiple runs opens avenues for automated parameter search methods. Models need to be tuned to match characteristics seen in reality, and due to the somewhat abstract nature of the parameters, it's necessary to employ some level of trial-and-error to finding the appropriate values. Doing this can be both time-consuming, and imprecise, whereas being able to run many iterations at once, and in shorter-periods of time, allows for better searching techniques effectively treating it as an optimisation problem.

Another noteworthy consideration is that of accessibility, many large-scale models are created for highly-parallel or at least high-end hardware. Ferguson [14], GSAM [34], FRED [41], and AceMod [8], are a few examples of this. Accessing high-compute resources can majorly inhibit research ability, especially when funding and time-sensitive access comes into play. Having an efficient implementation reduces hardware requirements, and as such a focus of this work was to implement it efficiently so that it runs acceptably on consumer hardware, both in terms of memory-usage and run-time.

Multiple interfaces of interaction

Often models will be something akin to a command-line utility, in that they require runtime (or at least initialisation) parameters and then run and produce an output on completion. This isn't necessarily a bad thing, most of the analysis on the results of the simulation require the context of the full-run (and thus feedback during run-time isn't useful), and often the end-state is the most desired information, whether it be total infections or otherwise. This is often supplemented by metrics created at intervals throughout the simulation, which allows for analysis of changes over time, the most common of which are represented in the standard SEIR graph (in the compartmentalised case). While these are often the most important, or at least desired, outputs, they fail to capture a lot of the spatial heterogeneity that distinguish spatially-explicit computational models like ABMs. Due to this, the other common output is a video, showing some form of overview of the space throughout the simulation, generally highlighting infections. These videos allow for more qualitative analysis, giving insight into if the spread acts within localities, and can be another way of verifying the model's correctness.

It was decided to aim to produce quantitative measurements at the end for reporting and analysis, consisting of both intermediary metrics and final statistics. On top of that, a visual interface with the simulation during execution was a key-feature, to both enable quick verification during development, and to provide a different view into complex spatial characteristics in the end result. Ideally the visual interface would be something akin to a game-engine, to allow for dynamic “camera” movement across the space, and to provide an avenue for future expansion of tweaking of parameters during the simulation for exploration purposes.

Ease of Use

As has been highlighted, a common characteristic of models is that they tend to be single-use, used for a specific piece of research and then abandoned, except perhaps sometimes used in subsequent research by the same team, see Ferguson’s papers[13, 14]. Some possible reasons for this have already been postulated, and in addition to those one that seems logical is that models produced as part of a paper of epidemiological results don’t tend to be written like most software. Frameworks and models designed with a focus on the engineering challenge, are designed to be maintainable and to be used as a tool over time, see GSAM [34] as an example, although ironically the code seems unavailable. Whereas the other models in question are often designed with a specific research question in mind, often reliant on the bespoke input dataset being used and the target processes of interest; these culminate in a somewhat unapproachable code-base (if released at all) with little documentation in the way of how to apply it to other problems and data-sets. It seems that this leads into a seemingly self-sustaining loop where each piece of research creates a new, unique, model, and the cost of doing so necessarily means a focus is put on the epidemiological results leading to the same set of problems.

This was viewed as such a large problem that it was the driving factor in not focusing on the epidemiological results of the model but instead on the engineering qualities of it. Focus was put on ensuring good architectural practices, approachable documentation, and as seen with the synthetic environment generator, flexibility and consistency in input styles to ensure the model wasn’t programmed to rely on a specific region or dataset.

4.2 Implementation

As the basis of the work, a programming language had to be chosen that could meet the established objectives. While some previous exploration had shown that Python wasn’t necessarily prohibitively slow, the layers of abstraction make it easy to write slow code without it being clear why. It is possible to write highly efficient code, especially when using optimised libraries like numpy or in-built functionalities of the language like list comprehensions, but having to be aware of the many subtleties that can induce slow-downs meant that a lower-level language was targeted. It was also viewed as necessary to pick one with a rich ecosystem for ease of development. Rust was chosen over C++ and Java due to its guarantees of memory safety and “fearless concurrency”; its greater control over low-level memory management, at least in terms of being easily accessible and explicit, compared to Java was seen as a large benefit due to the scales the simulation could be running at. Especially taking into consideration that there was zero development experience in the language prior, this work has shown that Rust is a language extremely well-suited to ABMs, and should be viewed as a competitive option for future research modelling at large-scales.

4.2.1 Simulation Time-Steps

Time-steps, also commonly called epochs, are discrete intervals of time across the simulation. Generally speaking for each time-step one iteration of the main simulation loop is ran, directly correlating computations with a chosen granularity of time-step. As such the choice has a large impact on run times, and proves to be a trade-off between fidelity and efficiency. It is readily apparent that running on a time-step of a month is going to give wildly different, and probably largely meaningless, results compared with running the loop every half a day. Attempting to pick the appropriate time-step becomes a matter of tuning.

An important consequence of changing a time-step is the impact this can have on the parameters of a simulation. If care isn't taken to separate choice of time-step from transmission probabilities for example, then their coupling inhibits changing the time-step later on. Doing this also impedes the ability to analyse benefits of choosing a shorter time-step, as it blocks the ability to compare the differences in outcome of two equivalent runs with differing time-steps.

Most similarly-placed models in literature run on a time-step of half an hour [14] or even half a day [6], although little reasoning seems to be given. Initially, for simplification, a half-hour time-step was chosen to match existing research, however it was kept to be configurable, which proved to be essential as it later became apparent with the inclusion of public transport, a time-step of a minute would probably be necessary due to how finely dispersed time-tabling information is, and indeed most commutes are shorter than half an hour.

4.2.2 The Graphical Interface

The first thing that ended up being implemented was a simple renderer of a pixel-buffer on an event-loop. This proved to be an indispensable part of the developmental process, providing rapid feedback on correctness, capturing a bug in the initial disease dynamics on a regular grid of agents where it wasn't spreading outwards from a point as expected, or for ensuring that the synthetic environment was loaded and parsed correctly. Contrary to the possible assumption that a "live" graphic of the simulation would be superfluous, this proved to actually be an extremely useful component to implement early. Future research and models within spatially-explicit simulations should consider this, as the basic implementation is easy to implement, relying on a simple 2-D grid of pixels, which can be easily rendered through a library in any sufficiently popular language.

A progression that unfortunately fell out of the remit of the work denoted here, was to have a more sophisticated graphical interface. Moving beyond a tool for verification in development, an integration with something like a game-engine would allow for a rendering pipeline that's separate from the simulation logic, where the user of the tool could zoom and pan on the space, something not present in most research models due to its non-immediately apparent utility.

Figure 4.1: A cropped and zoomed-in screenshot of the graphical interface for the south half of the London commuter ring

Figure 4.2: Number of fields in a cache-line with AoS or SoA Layouts

4.2.3 Agents

The agents within the simulation have a number of attributes associated to them. These include things like their allocated households and workplaces, and their disease state. The majority of which are read from the the synthetic environment Flatbuffer binary file. Some elements are necessarily constructed or modified at run-time, although review was being undertaken at the end of development to see what could be moved to the file. Each of the agent’s attributes were stored in vectors, in a pattern referred to as Struct-of-Arrays (SoA). The SoA pattern differs from the more common object-oriented philosophy of having each object’s attributes contained in a single struct, respectively known as Array-of-Structs (AoS).

The SoA pattern finds popular use within a style of development called data-oriented programming (DoP), as well as being familiar to those who work within the SIMD programming space. Of interest to ABMs is the effect this layout has on loops over large data structures. Due to pre-fetching and the cache mechanisms within the processor, smaller elements within a vector result in substantial increases in consecutive access. In ABMs it’s common to have loops of consecutive access across long lists of elements, for example looping over all agents to run infection calculations. These loops might have inter-dependence between elements, for example between an infected agent and a susceptible one, however the logic might rely upon one, or a subset, of the properties of each agent. For an infection calculation, it’s likely that the memory used to hold a reference to the agent’s household is irrelevant. The AoS approach results in the agent’s data being fetched in whole, including the unnecessary data, meaning fewer agents’ data fit within the cache.

An important addendum to this however is that consecutive access is key for performance gains, non-consecutive access can be much slower due to cache-misses and can result in thrashing. At the scales of the vectors in question, most of the data often cannot be in the cache at once. This has important considerations in the logic of the ABM model, these subtleties can have large impact on what might seem to be a worthwhile optimisation, for example the implementation of iterating over *only* infected agents without reordering will often result in non-consecutive access.

4.2.4 Containers

Due to the objective of including dynamic positioning, this work introduced the concept of *Containers*, later found out to be similar to that in Zhang’s [42]. Within the simulation containers represent places that an agent can be, at the present this includes households and workplaces, although future classifications would include public transport carriages, hospitals, shops, etc. Each container owns a position, a vector of inhabitants, a set of indices corresponding to agents that are within the space, and a *MixingStrategy* which is outlined later on. This acts similarly to the contact network found in other models, where it’s easy to directly access a specific agent’s current direct risk to infection, without naively looping and filtering over all agents.

4.2.5 Transmission Dynamics and Disease State

The disease related aspects are kept within two modular components, logic around disease states, and the transmission dynamics of the disease respectively.

Disease States

A simple SEIR compartmental model was selected for demonstrative purposes in the model, that is, agents can range between being Susceptible, Exposed, Infectious, and Recovered. Each state, called *DiseaseState* in the code, is encoded as an enum and is stored within a vector owned by the Agents component. This has the benefits previously outlined for AoS, and keeps the DiseaseState concerns separated from a lot of the rest of the code. This is important for future development, as it allows more complex disease models to be integrated easily, with either the addition of more compartments or a different type of model all together.

Mixing Strategies

At the core of the disease model is the method through which it's communicated. Referring back to some of the related work, one can see that a lot of static models group transmission into three methods, household, workplace, and community. These are often based on quite simple equations where risk is proportional to the number of infections in the respective population, weighed by some constant relating to contact likelihood within that group. This highlights an important consideration, that transmission dynamics and risk changes depending on the type of environment an agent is in at the time. This model therefore introduces the novel concept of a *MixingStrategy*, wherein each container has an associated *MixingStrategy*. For the purposes of demonstration the model implemented one called *Uniform* which calculates risk based on a rate that's proportional to the number of infected inhabitants of the container. This architecture however would allow for more complex behaviour, it would be possible to include social network graphs within workplaces where employees are more likely to interact with neighbouring colleagues or people on their floor. While this might prove to be too granular and unnecessary, it's useful to be able to assess the impact of introducing such behaviour, and then justify the generalisation of it within further research.

4.2.6 Dynamic Routing

Dynamic positioning adds the complication of needing to decide how agents move within the simulation. This has a relatively simple solution if travel time isn't considered important, on the given time-step the agent can be removed from one container and inserted into another. This isn't necessarily representative however, as people don't teleport, and if fine-grained containers like elevators at workplaces were to be added later on, different arriving times could have substantive effects. To solve this, upon a *Travel Event* a simple euclidean distance function was added to calculate the rough distance between containers. That distance is multiplied by a constant average travel speed based on travel method, this resultant process being referred to as *Direct Routing*. The agent is then added to the destination container when that time has elapsed. This all serves as a demonstration of functionality, and as a means to test if commute timings have any meaningful impact.

The core difficulties however occur with the inclusion of public transport. Within the UK it's estimated that 20% of commutes are taken on public transport [39], which means that, on large-scales as intended, in a day the simulation needs to calculate routes for millions of agents. A number of modern strategies exist for efficient path-finding on a weighted graph [3, 4, 18]. Contraction hierarchies seem to have the best general performance [5], and as evidence of Rust's rich ecosystem, an existing efficient implementation was accessible¹.

Due to time-constraints, only the total weight of the path (i.e. the commute time) was used, in a similar fashion to as described for the *Direct Routing* method. This is deemed to have little benefit in its current state and as such is toggled by a feature flag to avoid the execution slowdown. The underlying infrastructure however is there for further work to implement an actual public transit mobility simulation. This was a key aim for the project, and utilising the paths

¹https://github.com/easbar/fast_paths

from the contraction hierarchies, in conjunction with time-tabling information in the synthetic environment, it should be possible to model actual commuting journeys on public transit. This, in union with containers for transport carriages, could model complex mixing behaviours within commuting populations. This is a fairly novel area with little research, largely due to the complexity of it, and having a comprehensive simulation to test with it turned on, and without for comparison, would be advantageous in justifying or criticising its omission from other models.

4.2.7 Event-Driven Architecture

The Reasoning

While not initially included in the design, the development process led to the inclusion of an event-driven architecture. The time-line up to its inclusion helps to accentuate its purpose and its potential uses for other models, so it will be explained by the preceding events.

The original logic was based in a loop, where the simulation updates would be done a number of times for each render of the graphical interface. Each call to the simulation object to update itself corresponded to a new time-step, and thus using the initial time-step length of a half an hour, there would be 48 update loops per in-simulation day. For the sake of explanation, the logic can be majorly simplified and viewed as looping through each container and applying the infection simulation to the inhabitants, and then moving all agents to a new container if scheduled for that time-step.

The problem appears within the aforementioned “scheduling”, a time-step of half an hour limits people’s movements to being on the half-hour, and as a commute can be much shorter than that, a lot of the heterogeneity outlined in the time-step section is lost. Migrating to a shorter time-step directly multiplies the number of times the update loop has to be applied however, and as mentioned, public transport routing would need a time-step of about a minute. This would result in thirty times the original loops, which is a massive decrease to run-time, and infeasible for the largest scales.

To address this, the concept of an event was added, to allow for the update loop to focus on changing state within the simulation rather than needing to loop over all elements on every update. Looking at the simplified description of the logic, one can see this involves two core optimisations, one relating to how the infection simulation works, and the other applying to how often, and when, updates are applied.

Events

An event marks a change in agent positioning within the simulation. In the current implementation this comes in two variations, the *Travel*, and the *EnterContainer EventTypes*. The Travel event type handles agent’s departures from containers and their subsequent travel activities to the next place in their schedule, calling the routing logic described above. The EnterContainer event is rather self-explanatory, being responsible for agents entering containers.

Updating Disease Transmission

Referring back to a previous explanation about common transmission models, it’s usual to model infection risk as being uniformly proportional to time spent exposed to an infectious person, sometimes weighted by some constant for the type of interaction. This is the model implemented by the Uniform MixingStrategy, and it became apparent that as the risk is proportional to time spent mixing with a particular group of agents, it’s unnecessary to calculate the exposure at every time-step. The two factors that affect the exposure are the group of agents, and the time spent in that group. As such it’s only needed to calculate transmission upon a change in the group of agents, and perform that calculation as an aggregate of the time-steps since the last calculation.

This results in a major optimisation possibility, and was the driving reasoning behind adding events. Each entry or departure from a container is prefaced by a call to the transmission calculation with the time elapsed since the last change. It’s important to note that this aggregation is justifiable due to the length of time-steps in between changes. As long as the disease being modelled has an incubation period that isn’t substantially shorter than a day, then infections in between events

won't lead to compound infection risk being missed as events are (generally much more) frequent than a day and therefore the respective incubation period for the infection won't be anywhere near finished.

Implementing the Event Index

To benefit from these changes, it's necessary to efficiently find all events ending at the given time-step of the simulation in order to both run the transmission logic, and to find the agent's next event. The *EventIndex* is a data-structure that acts as a look-up for the set of events finishing at a given time-step. At its most simple level it works as follows:

```
for event in event_index.pop_front():
    if next_event = event.handle() is not None:
        event_index[time_step].push(next_event)
```

It's worth noting that in this implementation, only the next event for each agent is stored; upon handling the current event the subsequent event is added to the *EventIndex*. This is essential as storing millions of agent's complete schedules for an indeterminate simulation length is an excessive amount of memory.

How this is implemented is worth mentioning however as it had a number of considerations that could affect future attempts to reimplement it. To understand the final complexity of the implementation some of the other options will be analysed. As both the time-step size and simulation length is configurable in magnitude, the final time-step (and thus the span of indices into the *EventIndex*) is possibly very large. For instance, taking a time-step of one minute as might be necessary for transport routing, and a simulation length of a year, gives a final time-step of 525,600. Naively implementing the *EventIndex* as a vector therefore, has serious memory implications, especially if the memory for the lists of events at each index isn't carefully handled.

As each time-step consumes the front of the *EventIndex*, the memory used by the events at that index is able to be released. This is hard to capitalise on using vectors however, as they have good performance for removing from the back but not the front. As such an attempt was made to use a *HashMap* implementation for constant access and insertion but without the restriction of contiguous memory which removes the poor performance of removing the start of a list. This however, proved to be quite slow, even with the hash function removed (as indices are guaranteed to be unique).

Another option was that of a priority queue, which logically is well suited to the task, as each event's priority is its proximity to the current time-step. A number of Rust priority queue implementations were tried, including the std collection backed *binary_heap* and the open-source crate *priority_queue*. This also proved to be too slow at the larger scales of the simulation, which lead to an effort to implement a constant lookup, constant insertion, memory-efficient approach for the *EventIndex*.

To do this, a *VecDeque* is utilised, which is implemented on a growable ring buffer. This has the benefits of near-contiguous memory storage (aside from the partition in the ring), and efficient insertion and removal on both the front and back. The nature of being a ring buffer allows for reusing previously emptied memory, and being growable solves the uncertainty of how far in the future the next event might be. This is guaranteed to be relatively short as agents with events move at least once a day, so the underlying memory for the *VecDeque* won't be prohibitively large.

With the *VecDeque* as the underlying data-structure the update implementation requires accounting for the offset within the ring based off the current time-step:

```
for event in event_index.pop_front():
    if next_event = event.handle() is not None:
        let index_of_next_time = (next_event.end_time_step - time_step - 1)
        event_index.get_or_grow(index_of_next_time).push(next_event)
```

4.2.8 Agent Schedules

Agent schedules, or timetabling, is implemented very simply as proof of concept. As schools and other places of interest aren't implemented, currently only agents with a workplace move about in the simulation. For all agents with an occupational container, a starting *EnterContainer* event is

Figure 4.3: Ring Buffer with wrapping point highlighted

created, with a rudimentary generated start time. This start time is currently a random time-step between 04:00 and 11:00. Upon handling the EnterContainer event, a new Travel event is generated for half a day later to their home container.

This results in all employed agents going to work between 04:00 and 11:00, staying there for 12 hours, and then being routed home to stay there for 12 hours before repeating. This is a preliminary implementation that serves to demonstrate the simulation can handle agents each having unique schedules. Further work could look at extending event handling logic to create commuting patterns more representative of real life, and having more destinations and event types. This should be possible to do with random patterns rather than the traditional hard-coded schedules in way similar to how Zhang [42] describes.

4.3 Evaluation

As the implementation focused on architecture and technical challenges, it proves a little difficult to adequately evaluate it within the context of alternative models. This is indicative of a wider problem where defining appropriate comparisons can be hard due to an lack of definition for equivalence between models, but it's also accentuated in this case due to the features that were chosen to be implemented. Effort will be taken to highlight these considerations. With this in mind, the main criteria of evaluation will be taken from the high-level objectives established within subsection 4.1.1.

4.3.1 Modular Architecture

The code is largely modularised, with a generally good separation of concerns. Within the project there are the following core modules, agents, containers, disease, events, reporting, and routing. Some of these are broken up into sub-modules, the events module for example contains the implementation for the EventIndex, and for the Event components. An effort has been made to limit interaction with entities through an API where possible. This should allow for easier development of individual components as there are fewer places to update for changes due to a decoupling. This has direct impact in terms of thinking of the future of the project, disease related logic is contained within two core sub-modules, one relating to disease state, and the other to mixing. This will allow for the hot-swapping or updating of the chosen disease model, which was proven in development by moving from SIR to SEIR, although even a move to a non-compartmental model shouldn't require many changes outside of the disease module. Furthermore, encapsulating the mixing methodology into a *MixingStrategy* not only allows for the swapping of transmission models, but also for hybrid approaches, as each container has an associated strategy, which would allow different types of containers to have different transmission fidelities.

4.3.2 Dynamic Positioning

The simulation runner is spatially explicit in that containers have an associated position within the space, and agents are within one container at a time. The dynamism comes from agents entering and leaving containers, this can be seen in the graphical output of the simulation, as there's a periodic pulse of intensity (a marker of population-density at a pixel) as agents commute to and from work. The resultant implementation is therefore as spatially explicit as the synthetic environment provided as input. The implementation is also not proscriptive with what containers have to represent, (although they are currently used for workplaces) and as such containers could provide a way to have an even finer, or coarser, granularity than present.

As is outlined within subsection 4.1.1, the increased fidelity provided by modelling actual mobility within the simulation should be greatly beneficial to implementing more complex behaviours. Having less abstraction should make it easier to directly model common NPIs without needing to justify a generalisation of it. This also opens up a route to desirable but uncommon behaviour within ABMs, where agents activities can be reactive to the state. Trying to encode variations within the static network approach can be unintuitive, whereas one can somewhat naturally, i.e. directly, implement reactive behaviour like staying at home when symptomatic. Where further notable and presently relevant examples could cover shopping habits, choice of transit mode, lockdowns, etc. As was highlighted, the modular architecture, and thus the separation of the components relating to event handling, is what will facilitate the introduction of more complex and reactive behaviour patterns.

4.3.3 Efficiency

To evaluate the efficiency of the implementation, performance will be looked at in absolute and relative terms, where relative refers to within the context of other agent-based modelling. The latter case will be relevant to enable discussion over the needs, and general benefits, of allocating effort into efficiency.

Absolute Performance

The following benchmarks were ran on a consumer-grade desktop with the following specifications:

- Ryzen 5 2600 Six-Core Processor running at 3.40 GHz with a 567KB L1 Cache, 3.0MB L2 Cache and 16.0MB L3 Cache.
- 24GB of DDR4 RAM running at 1200MHz
- WD Blue SN550 1TB M.2 PCIe NVMe SSD with 2400MB/s Read, 2950MB/s Write, 410k/405k IOPS

Similarly to other places within this report, a set of six synthetic environments were used for benchmarking and testing. The set consists of files for: the Isle of Dogs, the Isle of Wight, the county of Devon, Greater Manchester, Wales, and the South half of the commuter ring of Greater London (which includes Central London and extends south of the M25 to include Guildford). These environments were then ran across hundreds of iterations each, and various combinations of run-time parameters of the simulation, generally in batches of 5-15 at a time.

Memory Usage Measuring the memory usage of a process can be a subtle and difficult procedure. As extremely accurate measurements weren't needed, estimates were manually collected from the Windows Task Manager "Memory" tab. The memory usage of the application mildly fluctuates (by a few percent) around the shown measurements and the average value was taken. These should serve as good indicators of the general requirements of the implementation, although the target of compilation might result in different memory requirements for 32-bit systems.

As Figure 4.4 shows, the largest synthetic environment of about 7 million agents used under 700MB of memory. Projecting the memory usage, as seen in Figure 4.5 for a UK population of 66 million gives an estimate of about 6GB of memory. This would fit on most modern consumer

Figure 4.4: Estimate memory usage

Figure 4.5: Estimate memory usage, projected for the UK's Population

devices, and as such would prove to be a huge benefit for easy reproducibility, verification, and open-source contribution.

Regarding potential future performance, the memory is currently mainly allocated by three components, namely agents, workplaces, and public transit. As the graphs show, these are likely to scale linearly with population size. This seems to hold even when considering public transit, where the size of the graph grows quickly with region size, as can be seen by the memory usage of Wales which has a much larger transit network than the others but is still fitted well to the line. Despite the growth of network size, it's still likely dwarfed in memory by the quantity of agents and buildings that come with the increased region. With the likely introduction of schools, hospitals and other similar entities, memory usage would be expected to continue to be linear albeit with a steeper gradient.

Run Time Performance Included within the repository is a selection of benchmarks of key data-structures and core logic, for instance the EventIndex and accompanying event-handling. These run using Criterion², a Rust crate for incredibly accurate (down to the single instruction level) benchmarking and statistical analysis of performance. These low-level benchmarks have informed design decisions and were utilised throughout changes in order to test for regression.

²<https://docs.rs/crate/criterion/>

They are however, not particularly relevant in the scope of this evaluation, as overall run times are more interesting for holistic analysis.

Figure 4.6: Mean run times for 100 days

Figure 4.7: Mean run times for 100 days, projected for the UK's population

Figure 4.6 establishes a confidently linear relationship between execution time and number of agents. Once again projecting this in Figure 4.7 to a representative 66 million agents for the UK, results in an estimated runtime of about 7000 seconds, or roughly 2 hours for 100 days of simulation.

The data in Figure 4.6 consisted of 50 iterations for each environment ran in batches of 5, although previous tests had been ran with 100-200 iterations each with very similar results. The smaller number of iterations was chosen as previously larger tests were ran in batches of 15, which resulted in faster overall run times but CPU throttling which affected the values. Figure 4.6, Figure 4.7, and Figure 4.8 have standard deviations shown for each model. However as is evident, the bars are generally not visible at this scale, as the simulations tend to have very consistent run times. It's worth noting that the simulations ran for exactly 100 days each, rather than stopping once the infection had died out as some other models might do, which results in higher stochasticity.

Figure 4.8 shows that the run time is also linear with respect to the number of days being simulated. It was ran on the largest dataset of the south half of the London commuter ring for 100 iterations each per simulation length.

Figure 4.8: Mean run times for varying simulation lengths of S. London Commuter Ring

Difficulties in Establishing Comparable Works

Establishing a set of models to compare against is not a straightforward task. Within epidemiology agent-based modelling spans a large range of research areas. Models encapsulate different behaviours, cover different regions, have different granularities, run for different simulation lengths, and many other aspects in the long list of differentiating factors. Many of these factors are evidently significant when it comes to comparison, in that they may invalidate direct comparison between benchmarks. The significance of other factors might prove difficult to gauge and thus go undetected.

Even after a set of comparable models has been selected, it can prove impossible to directly compare them due to the aforementioned popular choice to not include simulation code or datasets. This means that models can't be downloaded and ran on comparable hardware, and even in cases where code is released, that code can often require hugely-parallel compute sources or highly specialised environments inhibiting comparison on equivalent hardware. In lieu of code, one would hope to be able to use values given within the papers. However more often than not, the papers and accompanying supplementary information usually solely focus on the epidemiology and thus fail to mention performance or other characteristics of the implementation. In their systematic review, Willem et al. describe the “amount of missing information on the platform or other technical details” [41] as being “noteworthy, especially when the model is not described elsewhere or open-source”.

Because of this, the following evaluation will necessarily stray from quantitative methods, instead focusing on holistic analysis with specific examples drawn from literature accompanied by relevant considerations.

4.3.4 Relative Performance

To be able to evaluate the performance of the current implementation, within the context of the wider domain, it's necessary to collect some indication of the performance of other models.

FluTE FluTE, self described as a “publicly available stochastic influenza epidemic simulation model” [6], is an ABM that was designed with a focus on influenza. Willem et al. identify that FluTE [6] uses “approximately 80 megabytes of memory per million simulated individuals” and “simulating an epidemic in a population of 10 million people can take up to two hours” [41].

FRED Willem et al. also describe FRED, a “Framework for Reconstructing Epidemic Dynamics”, another ABM focused on influenza [20] as needing “750 - 1000 megabytes of memory required per million simulated individuals” [41]. The paper describing FRED states that “a simulated pandemic

over the entire U.S. population requires approximately 200GB of memory and takes approximately 4 hours using 16 threads” [20].

AceMod AceMod [8] is an agent-based modelling framework for studying influenza epidemics in Australia. AceMod runs on a “High Performance Computing” service at the University of Sydney, comprised of “4264 cores of computing capacity, consisting of 136 standard compute nodes, two high memory nodes (512 GB), three very high memory nodes (6 TB), and five GPU compute nodes, under a “Fair Share” resource allocation model (e.g., no more than 288 cores)” [8]. “A typical run of 180 days of an epidemic is simulated on an HPC node in 42 minutes, so that each scenario covering 10 runs varying over infection “seeds” is complete and integrated within seven hours”.

CovidSim The supplementary information of Ferguson et. al’s 2006 paper describes the model that was later adapted for COVID-19 (consequently dubbed CovidSim). “The simulation was written in C using the OpenMP 2.0 SMP libraries. The US simulation used some 55GB of RAM, and each realization ran in 1-2 hours on 8 CPU Opteron 854 based servers, and in 2-5 hours on 16 CPUs of the NCSA SGI Altix 3700 system (‘cobalt’)” [14].

Large-scale agent-based social simulation Within the “System Performance” section of Zhang’s thesis it states that a simulation run for 19.6 million agents takes “around 40 hours for one simulation run” [42] where one simulation run has a length of 30 days. Despite claims of efficient memory usage, there seems to be a lack of measurements or estimates, and also a missing description of the hardware used for the simulations. The current implementation shares many similarities with that of the model described in Zhang’s thesis [42]. Both implement logic around physical containers, have dynamic movement of agents, at least partially include public transport logic, and opt for an event-driven architecture.

One of the main objectives of this work was to be able to support simulating complex behaviour at large-scales. As such all of the above-mentioned models were chosen for their targeted scales. Models that have been in prominent recent literature are often of a much smaller scale, 500,000 agents, [22] 10,000 agents, [36] or even as few as 300. [37]

In terms of that main objective, the current implementation has been tested up to 7 million agents, although as shown, analysis suggests it should be able to comfortably support much higher numbers. At those scales it supports highly granular timing for behaviours due to its event-driven architecture, is dynamically spatially explicit, and has the foundation for advanced mobility modelling with the inclusion of public transport. These behaviours all generally have meaningful implications on run time performance, and thus are largely the factors focused on in joint with potential scale of simulations.

Comparing with the exemplary models therefore, it would seem that the current implementation is very well placed. From direct comparison it seems that it has much shorter run times than that of Zhang [42] and FluTE [6]. The first of which is to be expected as Zhang’s implementation has a wider scope and covers a greater variety of behaviours while also claiming to have more fleshed out public transport logic. The better performance when compared to FluTE is of note when considering that FluTE works with 2 time steps per simulated day [6] rather than the 48 in this work used for the benchmarks above.

There’s a less clear comparison between the current work and CovidSim [14] and FRED [20]. The results claimed there are ran on powerful architectures with much higher memory budgets and likely better computational power. Despite this the current benchmarks seem to suggest comparable or better performance, despite being mostly single-threaded and on a consumer desktop with much lower memory budget. It’s worth noting that both models have implementations that cover more than just the workplaces present in the current model, but neither have the high fidelity and both have simpler update logic.

It seems that the current implementation either matches, or in most cases, outperforms, current alternatives. It achieves this while having an infrastructure with foundations set up for more complex behaviour and it supports higher fidelity. Further analysis will be needed with any future development, as the implementation of further behaviours and more spatial locations, as well as

finishing the public transit logic, could greatly impact performance. Despite this, such potential decreases to performance are either likely to be linear (and thus comparable) as explained above. Even if they should not prove to be linear, the current implementation has a large amount of room for improvement, as the main updating logic surrounding disease transmission and the event-loop is single threaded. This should be relatively easily parallelisable with Rust with crates like Rayon³, which has given 10% - 70% speed increases in other parts of the code.

4.3.5 Necessary Efficiency

The proposed benefits of an efficient implementation that were outlined in subsection 4.1.1 were directly seen during development. Fast run times allowed for rapid iteration, which in turn facilitated faster overall development. It's also allowed for larger scale benchmarks, with hundreds of iterations being ran simulating a range of five days to two years. Thousands of iterations and millions of time steps have been simulated on a single consumer desktop PC in a couple of weeks in the making of this report. This also was enabled by the efficient use of memory, as it allowed for multiple iterations to be ran in parallel, with some of the benchmarks having 15 simulations of 7 million people being ran in tandem. This will directly affect confidence in future results, as it will allow aggregations over larger numbers of stochastic runs, strengthening arguments about intrinsic emergent properties.

³<https://docs.rs/rayon/>

5 | Conclusions and Future Work

5.1 Overview

This report presented a new approach to the process of creating an epidemiological agent-based model. It identified a common failure to distinguish between the input model and the simulation model, and proposed a way to address the two components. The goals set out for the work were largely achieved, and it paves the way for a large amount of future research by providing a solid and extensible foundation. In-line with the critique posed at the majority of models, the code has been open-sourced on Github¹ under the permissive Apache License 2.0.

The project focuses on utilising open-source data to ensure ease of access and reproducibility. It demonstrates that such streams are viable without the need of acquiring licenses and usage agreements, which greatly removes the barrier to entry. The result is a pipeline with sophisticated behaviour that demonstrates the benefits of having a well-structured output format. This format is verified by an extremely efficient implementation of a large-scale epidemiological simulation, which minimises compromise between complexity and speed. The development process of the simulation highlighted the strengths of the environment generator, allowing for the creation of bespoke datasets of regions around the UK in a matter of hours easily chosen for spatial characteristics, size, location, and more. The components outlined in this report pave the way for analysis into if higher fidelity is actually substantive in its benefit, by facilitating the creation of more detailed synthetic environments and making it viable to run comparative simulations at finer granularities.

5.2 The Resultant Models

The focus of the work was on the technical challenges, and the underlying architecture, of creating an ABM. As such it leaves room for research into appropriate tuning for transmission parameters, as well as expanding the selection of input datasets in the environment generator to ensure they're rigorously justified before being used to draw conclusions on the epidemiology. Despite this, the decision to use logical placeholders within such points of the implementation allows for a general sanity-check of behaviour. This acts as a useful avenue to evaluate the overall efficacy of the components in union. Example analyses are supplied in the included reporting tool within the repository, which ties simulation results to their respective synthetic environments. The analysis tools were used to generate the majority of the graphs in this report, as well as the relevant benchmarks for the simulations.

A common output of similar models is a set of SEIR model curves as demonstrated in Figure 5.1. While the specific values involved in the graphs aren't particularly relevant due to the lack of parameter tuning, the overall behaviour of the simulation matches expectations of a standard SEIR model. Each graph within Figure 5.1 actually consists of 100 iterations drawn on top of each other. The fact that the curves look like relatively thick lines implies that despite some stochasticity within the simulation (mostly from the distribution of people infected at the start), the transmission dynamics are consistent across iterations. This is likely due to the relatively high seed infection chance, where roughly 1% of the population is infected at the start.

Figure 5.2 displays simulations of each environment for 45 iterations across 6 seed infection chances, 10%, 1%, 0.1%, 0.01%, 0.001%, and 0.0001%. In contrast to Figure 5.1, the iterations

¹<https://github.com/Alfred-Mountfield/outbreak-sim>

are aggregated by their mean (shown as a solid line) and standard deviation (shown as a semi-transparent filled area). One can see that in the current implementation the seed infection chance has a large impact on the transmission dynamics. There seems to be a threshold seed chance where across all regions the transmission dynamics of the disease are near identical as described above. However once the seed percentage lowers below that threshold a lot of variation in runs can be seen, as demonstrated by the filled areas. Below that threshold there seems to be two cases, either the disease fails to sustain exponential growth and fluctuates around a point, or it dies out. The latter case is to be expected in a lot of runs if there's a very low seed percentage, however the prior case provides an interesting point of discussion.

The lower seed percentages show interesting differences between the synthetic environments. The Isle of Wight, and Devon environments have much higher variance than that of the others. This is likely to be caused by different spatial structures in the environments when it comes to the spatial distribution of allocated workplaces. Such effects would be lost at higher seed infection chances as that would lead to a higher homogeneity in infections across the population thus dimming the effects of connections between regions. This is likely indicative of inadequate mixing in the current implementation of the model. Due to only implementing workplaces, agents are missing some key mixing networks present in real-life, schools, friendship groups, et cetera. The two environments are less population dense than the other selected regions, and the populations are less evenly distributed across the space, resulting in an accentuation of the underestimated mixing between clusters of populations. Where simulations were started with smaller infected populations, underestimating mixing would also explain why the transmission failed to become exponential in most cases, instead jumping from workplace to workplace through households without really expanding.

This demonstrates a major benefit of the approach, in that the consistent format of the synthetic environment allows for painless direct comparisons between regions due to their hot-swappable nature. This will facilitate further research into studying how the spatial heterogeneity of regions impacts transmission characteristics. This is further assisted by the direct link between the output report and the model's synthetic environment input. The report analysis tool is able to read the synthetic environment file and examine aspects like population density, workplace distributions, et cetera. This allows for direct comparisons between results and input regions in a way that wasn't easily possible to do previously, to identify dependent variables and principle components of the synthetic environments.

5.3 Future Work

In addition to fixing the discrepancies between population density and OSM building data, a number of future development possibilities are highlighted. These constitute a subset of the large number of continuations possible from the current pipeline.

- Migrating from the UK Public Transport graph to using GTFS to allow regions selected from anywhere on the globe
- Extending the workplace allocation process to cover creating and allocating schools
- Locating data-sources on Hospitals and their inclusion in the model
- Adding care-homes, whose importance was proven by COVID-19's effect in the UK
- Developing an interface for region-specific datasets like census data
- Optimisations on memory usage and speed

5.4 Concluding Remarks

The analysis of the resultant models demonstrates the utility and potential of the current components. The synthetic environment generator presents a promising foundation for automated synthetic environment generation. It explores the feasibility of using novel granular data-sources to increase fidelity and better capture spatial heterogeneity. The benefits of having an automated

pipeline with consistent outputs can be seen in the variety of environments easily created for this report. If future work is undertaken to remove the current limitation to UK geographies, the generator should prove to be a useful tool that greatly saves on the time needed for new agent-based models, while perhaps facilitating research in less-developed areas of the world. The simulation runner further verifies the benefits of using a low-level language with greater control over memory management. Rust presents an interesting option as a language for future models, as its guarantees around concurrency and memory safety would prove to be an incredibly useful attribute for future work at large-scales. It should allow for more time to be spent on simulation logic and epidemiological research rather than bug-fixing and architecting. The work undertaken in this report ultimately opens many promising avenues for further research, while also adding to and improving on current approaches, showing that higher fidelities are not only possible, but viable at scale.

Figure 5.1: SEIR Curves for 90 days of simulation with 1% seed infection chance (100 iterations)

Figure 5.2: SEIR Curves with varying seed infection chances (mean across 45 iterations with standard deviation)

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